

Eine widerspruchsfreie Lösung ist zum gegenwärtigen Zeitpunkt – fehlende, eindeutige Grabungsergebnisse – und mit der gegenwärtigen – konventionellen – Methode nicht möglich: zu komplex sind die Verknüpfungen zwischen den in den Texten genannten Orte.

1. M. Guichard, « Au pays de la Dame de Nagar » in : D. Charpin, J.-M. Durand (ed.), *Florilegium Marianum II: Recueil d'études à la mémoire de Maurice BIROT, Mémoires de NABU* 3, Paris 1994, 235-272, bes. 240-244.

2. V. Haas, M. Wäfler, Möglichkeiten der Identifizierung des Tall al-Ḥamīdiya in : S. Eichler et al., *Tall al-Ḥamīdiya I*, OBO SA 4, Freiburg i. Ü/Göttingen 1985, 53-76 ; M. Wäfler, Ta'idu : *Stolica Panstwa Mitanni, Xenia Posnaniensia* II, 1993, 4-18.

3. Eine gute, leicht verständliche Einführung zum Problem bietet nach wie vor : G. Olsson, *Distance and Human Interaction: A Review and Bibliography*, Philadelphia 1965.

4. Vgl. z.B. F. Joannès, *ARMT XXVI/2*, Paris 1988, 235.

5. M. Wäfler, Historische Geographie : Theoretische Perspektiven in : O. Rouault (ed.), *La Djéziré et l'Euphrate syriens, Actes du Colloque International* : Paris, 21-24 juin 1993 (im Druck).

6. So wohl auch : D. Charpin, « Une Campagne de Yahdun-Lim en Haute-Mésopotamie » in : D. Charpin, J.-M. Durand (ed.), *Florilegium Marianum II: Recueil d'études à la mémoire de Maurice BIROT, Mémoires de NABU* 3, Paris 1994, 177-200, bes. 180.

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32) The root of *išittu* 'storehouse' – Both *AHw* and *CAD* record this word equating the Sumerian *èrim* (URU X GAR) among other Sumerian words, but only *AHw* (p. 395a) records the plural *iš-na-ti-ia*, citing with a question mark F. Delitzsch, *HWB* 146a, which states : « *ina iš-na-ti-ia* (Ideogr. URU x GAR) *ša-ak-na* ... Lond. Frgm. (nach G. Smith). » The present writer's interest had been aroused by finding another such plural :

èrim-zi-za ku₄-ra-ni-šè
ana i-šit-ti-ka kit-ti
dìm-me-er-e-ne èrim-ZA-ne-ne-a hé
ilānu^{meš} iš-na-ti-šú-nu

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(ZA in 19 is no doubt an error for A.) R. Borger kindly provided the number of the fragment quoted by Delitzsch and further quoted by W. von Soden, and also referred me to J. Krecher, *SKI* 116 n. 345, which also quotes this line, from an unpublished copy of F. H. Weissbach :

èrim-ma ám-mar-mar-ra-mu ki [...]
ina iš-na-ti-ia šá-ak-na-a-ti[m ...]
K 4953 12-13

Thus the plural of *išittu* 'storehouse' is *išnātu* and so the root is *'šn*. Cognates occur in Classical Hebrew and in Aramaic. In Deuteronomy 28 : 8 and Proverbs 3 : 10 *'āsām* 'storehouse' occurs both times in the plural with suffix : *'a sāmēkā* « your (sing.) storehouses. » This same form also occurs in an emendation of Psalm 104 : 13, and in the text of a Post-Biblical document from the Dead Sea scrolls 4Q416 2 : 2 (see R.H. Eisenman and M. Wise, *The Dead Sea Scrolls Uncovered*, Shaftesbury, Dorset, 1992, p. 245, and D.J.A. Clines (ed.), *The Dictionary of Classical Hebrew* 1, Sheffield, 1993, p. 346a). The verb *'āsam* « gather (in a store) » occurs twice in a 7th century Hebrew letter on an ostrakon (J. Naveh, *IEJ* 10, 1960, 129ff. 5-7 ; cf. F.M. Cross, *BASOR* 165, 1962, 44 n. 43). In Jewish Aramaic the noun 'storehouse' occurs, variously vocalised *'assānā'*, *'asnā'*, or *'usnā'* (see the standard dictionaries), and the verb *'sn* 'gather' occurs in Syriac (C. Brockelmann, *Lexicon Syriacum*² p. 35b). Despite the variation in the final consonant *m/n*, and the irregular correspondence of Akk. *š* and Hebrew/Aramaic *s* (note that the LA *i-si-te-ia* in *ABL* 124 is taken as « tower » in *SAA* V 120), there is really no doubt that the Akkadian and Hebrew/Aramaic words are related.

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33) ^dnin-mar-ki-ga – Dans *ZA* 75 (1985) 1-3, R.M. Whiting a attiré l'attention sur le parallélisme structurel évident entre *OIP* 99 p. 51 : 186 sq. (cité à titre d'exemple) *isin₂ bulug₄ an ki / ^dnin-isin₂ za₃-me* et *OIP* 99 p. 51 : 165 sq. *mar bala¹ an ki / ^dnin-mar za₃-me*. Il en déduisit que « Mar was a pre- or protohistoric geographical name » (p. 1), et que ^dnin-MAR(.KI) doit être lu ^dnin-mar(ki). Spéculations et étymologies populaires seraient à l'origine des – plus tardifs – (E₂-)^dNin-MAR.KI^{ki}, ^dNin-KI.MAR.RA et ^dNin-mar-ra (p. 3 ; translit. de Whiting).

Cette hypothèse (à laquelle je souscris dans une large mesure) fut accueillie en général favorablement (e.g. J. Bauer, *BiOr.* 46 [1989] 640 et M. Civil, *Mél. Sjöberg* 56). M. Krebernik en revanche (*ZA* 76 [1986] 199), et après lui quelques autres, se montrèrent plus réticents, rappelant l'existence de ^dnin-MAR.GI₄ (*OIP* 99 83 iv 4' // 84 ii 3' = A. Alberti, *SEL* 2 [1985] 11 : 201 = P. Mander, *Il Pantheon di Abu-Šalābīḥ*, Napoli, 1986 p. 28 : 205) « die —falls zugehörig— syllabische Lesungen ki/gi₄ erweist! » (loc. cit.)². Pour concilier ces faits apparemment contradictoires, P. Michalowski (*LSU* p. 87) avança une explication différente : « early mar-gi₄ was reinterpreted as mar^{ki} already in ED III times and was later the subject of some confusion. One line of analysis viewed mar^{ki} as an old geographical name and another parallel interpretation saw in it an old writing for an element ki-mar, hence the OB toponym é-ki-mar (*SLTN* 103 7', 8') ».

Dans cette note, j'aimerais attirer l'attention sur quelques formes plaidant en faveur d'une lecture ^dnin-mar-ki-k(/g), généralisée dès Ur III et probablement fréquente antérieurement (pour les arguments avancés par F. Thureau-Dangin et E. Sollberger, v. infra) :

– ^dnin-MAR.KI n'a pas une finale en /r³, le texte souvent cité à l'appui de cette hypothèse (*PBS* 10/4 6 : 9 = *LSU* 168 B) ne portant pas ^dnin-MAR.KI-ra-ke₄ (copie), mais ^dnin-mar-ki-ra (datif!) [eš₃] (Michalowski, photo). Si les morphèmes de l'erg. ou du gén. (+ erg./loc.) sont graphiquement explicités, l'erg. est ^dnin-mar-ki-ke₄ et le gén. (+ erg./loc.) ^dnin-mar-ki-ka(-ke₄/ka) (pour l'ép. présarg., cf. par ex. *Enetarzi* 1 i 2 et v 1 ; passim à partir d'Ur III).

– Le NP « Celui de Ninmarki », normalement ^dnin-mar-ki-ka, est écrit parfois ^dnin-mar-ki-ga⁴ à l'abs. (*TCTI* I 950 i 2), à l'erg. (*TMH NF* 1/2 253 : 8 [suivi de u₃ ḫu-ud-da!] et 254 : 3) et au gén. (*TMH NF* 1/2 247^a/247^b : 15), au gén. aussi ^dnin-mar-ki-ga-ka (*TMH NF* 1/2 253 : 1). En d'autres termes, le -ki de ^dnin-mar-ki-k(/g) se comporte exactement comme celui de ^den-ki-k(/g).

– Dans la *Canonical Temple List* publiée récemment par A.R. George (*House Most High* [...] = *Mesopotamian Civilizations* 5, Winona Lake, 1993), ^dnin-mar-ki-k/g a été réinterprétée par ^dnin-mar-ku₃-g (1. 502)⁵.

Si l'on essaye de résumer les principaux arguments avancés en faveur de chacune des deux hypothèses, les points suivants méritent d'être rappelés :

^dnin-mar-ki

– L'existence de ^dnin-mar, attestée à Fāra (Krebernik, *ZA* 76 190 *SF* 5/6 : 22, *NTSŠ* pl XXI 205 iii 2 et H. Steible, *FAOS* 9/1 [1991] 125 citant **TSŠ* 102 iii 4 [sic!]), à Abū Šalābīḥ (*OIP* 99 p. 51 : 166) et à Lagaš (*VS NF* 9 69 iv 13' et *ITT* 5/2 pl. 70, 9207 i' 3' [v. infra]).

^dnin-mar-ki(-k/g)

– La notation systématique de KI dans les inscriptions d'Urnanše⁶ (Sollberger, *ZA* 50 [1952] 10 n. 1).
– La quasi-absence, à époque ancienne, d'un NG mar^(ki) (Sollberger, *BiOr.* 16 [1959] 118)⁷.
– La graphie sporadique e₂-^dnin-mar-ki^{ki} (Thureau-Dangin, *RA* 15 [1918] 26 sq. et Sollberger, *AfO* 17 [1954-1955] 34 sq. n. 126⁸).

– ^dnin-mar-gi₄ (Krebernik), pour autant que ce ne soit vraiment qu'une graphie de ^dnin-mar-ki.

– La finale en /k(/g), pas en /r⁹.

– Les rares attestations de ^dnin-mar-ki-ga⁹.

– La réinterprétation tardive par ^dnin-mar-ku₃-g.

Pour rendre compte de ces faits, deux hypothèses sont a priori envisageables :

1) ^dnin-mar et ^dnin-mar-ki(/^dnin-mar-gi₄) sont des divinités distinctes. Cette solution semble toutefois exclue par ^dnin-mar-ama-ḡu₁₀ (*ITT* 5/2 pl. 70, 9207 i' 3') // ^dnin-mar-ki-ama-ḡu₁₀ (ib. pl. 67, 9702 rev. ii' 3')¹⁰.

2) Au plus tard à l'époque d'Ur III, ^dnin-mar-ki-k(/g) a été rapproché de ^den-ki-k(/g), la forme originelle du nom étant plus vraisemblablement ^dnin-mar^(ki) (Whiting) que l'hapax ^dnin-mar-gi₄ (Michalowski), car il faudrait alors postuler une cascade de réinterprétations déjà à époque ancienne : ^dnin-mar-gi₄ > ^dnin-mar-ki > ^dnin-mar^(ki) > ^dnin-mar-ki-k(/g), etc.! Il me paraît plus simple d'y voir soit une divinité différente, soit une réinterprétation isolée de ^dnin-mar-ki.

1. Il serait tentant de rapprocher bala de (ḡeš)bala (probabl. /bala(ḡ)/ v.s. ; cf. ḡešbala // balaḡ [Isin *6 : 53], la glose *ma-la-gu-um* dans la « Sign-list » d'Ebla 128 et l'akkadien *pilakk/qqu*, qui alterne avec bulug dans K. Volk, *FAOS* 18 40 : bala-bala-ḡa₂ (H 2 K xxix 5) // bulug_{bu}-bulug-ga (commentaire de Volk p. 223).

2. Possibilité déjà envisagée par R.D. Biggs, *OIP* 99 p. 55.

3. Dans *DP* 55 vii 5-7 (niḡ₂-ḡeš-tag-ga / ^dnin-MAR.KI-ra / [x-x¹-la], -ra est probablement le morphème du datif).

4. Cf. F.R. Kraus, *WO* 8 (1975-1976) 188 et n. 7, H. Waetzoldt, *WO* 9 (1977) 204 et H. Neumann, *Šulmu* 4 (1993) 229 et n. 42 sq.

5. L'explication proposée par George (p. 36) me semble inutilement compliquée.

6. Sinon seulement dans *umma^{ki}* (*Urn.* 51 rev. i 3, iii 10, iv 7 et vi 1) ; cf. toutefois F. Pomponio, *RSO* 63 (1989) 26 sqq.

7. Les deux attestations nA de MAR^{ki} citées par Bauer (*BiOr.* 46 640) ne sont naturellement pas un contre-argument ; comp. MAR^(ki) = Amurru (Maul 'Herzberuhigungsklagen' 182 avec litt.) ?

8. Pour les « listes géographiques de Tell Ḥarmal », cf. maintenant *MSL* 11 56, Appendix 2 i 24.

9. Serait en principe compatible avec une lecture mara(-k/g) de MAR, pour laquelle toutefois rien ne plaide mis à part S^bB 279.

10. 9202 « f. i' » 3' sqq. // 9207 « rev. ii' » 2' sqq., 9202 « f. ii' » 3' sqq. = 9207 « rev. i' » 2' [sqq.], 9202 « rev. ii' » 1' sqq. = 9207 « f. i' » 1' sqq., 9202 « rev. i' » 5' = (?) 9207 « f. ii' » 1'.

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34) The Earliest Evidence for Nebuchadnezzar IV's Reign – As it is known, the Babylonians revolted twice against Darius I. The first rebellion led by Nebuchadnezzar III was suppressed by Darius himself soon after December 18, 522 B.C. The exact date of the beginning of the second revolt is unknown. According to the Behistun inscription (par. 49f.), this revolt was led by Arakha, the son of a certain Haldita. He claimed to be Nebuchadnezzar (IV) son of Nabonidus. Documents dated in his reign come from Babylon, Borsippa, Sippar, Uruk, Ur and some other cities. On November 27, 521 the Babylonians were defeated, their leader captured and executed.

As seen from the Behistun inscription (par. 21 and 31), after his victory over the Babylonians in December 522, Darius stayed in Babylon directing military operations of his generals in Persia, Media and other countries of the empire and then went to Media. On January 21, 521, when his army won a battle against the rebellious Medes, Darius was still in Babylon. But on May 7, 521 he won a victory in Media himself. Thus, he arrived in Media some time between January 21 and May 7, 521.

While Darius was in Media, the Babylonians made a new attempt to gain independence. According to Parker and Dubberstein, the earliest known document dated in the reign of Nebuchadnezzar IV is YBC 4049 (see now YOS 17, no. 286) drafted on V/16/1 (August 25, 521). The same authors have rejected Cameron's assumption (AJSL 58, 1941, p. 318) that, to judge from Nbk.12, Nebuchadnezzar IV had already revolted in month IV (before August 10, 521), since the month sign and the year sign in the tablet are damaged. They suppose that until the beginning of September, 521 Darius was recognized as ruler of Babylonia and then Nebuchadnezzar IV revolted toward late August (*Babylonian Chronology*, p. 16). It can be added to this that by now the earliest known document dated in the reign of Nebuchadnezzar IV is OECT 10, no. 406 drafted on V/14/1 (August 23, 521).

It seems to me that the date of Nebuchadnezzar IV's revolt can be reconsidered now using new prosopographical evidence. CT 57, no. 118 was composed on III/8 of the 1st regnal year of Nebuchadnezzar (without any titlature). It records that 1 mina and 30 shekels of silver were paid to a certain Šamaš-iqīša as « the purchase price for sheep ». The document comes from the archives of the Ebabbara temple in Sippar. As far as I know, Šamaš-iqīša is not referred to in documents from Sippar dated in the reign of Nebuchadnezzar II but he is frequently mentioned in texts from Sippar composed during Nabonidus' and Darius I' reigns. For instance, according to Dar.186 drafted in the 5th year of Darius, 35 shekels of silver were paid to Šamaš-iqīša as « the purchase price for oxen ». In the 1st year of Nabonidus the Ebabbara administration paid Šamaš-iqīša 15 shekels of silver for two « fattened oxen » (CT 55, no. 692). During the same year, he (this time he is called the son of Šamaš-aha-iddina; the same patronymic occurs also in several other texts) sold some livestock to the temple, including « two fattened oxen » for the regular offerings (CT 55, no. 699; see also *ibid.*, nos. 96,173; CT 57, no. 68; Nbn.205, 249; cf. CT 57, no. 69, 5 where he bears the title *rab būli*, « overseer of the herds »). He is referred to in documents drafted from the 1st year of Nabonidus to the 5th year of Darius I (555-517) as a person who was supplying the Ebabbara temple with sheep and oxen. CT 57, no. 118 cannot be assigned to the reign of Nebuchadnezzar II, since in this case the gap between this document and Dar.186 would be 87 years. Neither can it be attributed to Nebuchadnezzar III, since it was drafted in the third month of the Babylonian calendar, while he ruled Babylonia from the 7th until the beginning of the 10th month. Consequently, the document should be assigned to the reign of Nebuchadnezzar IV. If this is the case, it was composed on June 19, 521. Now we can safely accept Cameron's assumption that Nbk.12 belongs to the reign of the same king. It mentions Marduk-nāšir-apli of the Egibi business house, who is known from many documents dated in the reign of Darius I.

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35) An Unidentified Document from Xerxes' Reign and the Ebabbara Temple – S. Dalley has published a number of Achaemenid legal documents in her book *A Catalogue of the Akkadian Cuneiform Tablets in the Collections of the Royal Scottish Museum* (Edinburg, 1979). The text no. 72 of the Catalogue is described by her as a « receipt of linseed and another commodity » drafted in the 2nd regnal year of Artaxerxes (i.e., 463 B.C., if Artaxerxes I is meant). The text is reported to have come from Sippar (p. 4). The body of the document is much damaged but the rest of it is well preserved. Its date is the 2nd year of *Ah-šū-hu-šū* LUGAL *Par-su*